

Adsorption, Organization, and Rheology of Catanionic Layers at the Air/Water Interface

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Abstract

We have investigated the adsorption and organization at the air/water interface of catanionic molecules released from a dispersion of solid-like catanionic vesicles composed of myristic acid and cetyl trimethylammonium chloride at the 2 : 1 ratio. These vesicles were shown recently to be promising foam stabilizers. Using Brewster angle microscopy, we observed the formation of a catanionic monolayer at the air/water interface composed of liquid-condensed domains in a liquid-expanded matrix. Further adsorption of catanionic molecules forced them to pack, thereby forming a very dense monolayer that prevented further vesicle rupture by avoiding contact of the vesicles with air. Moreover, confocal fluorescence microscopy revealed the presence of layers of intact vesicles that were progressively creaming toward this catanionic monolayer; the surface tension of the vesicle dispersion remained constant upon creaming. The catanionic monolayer behaved as a soft glassy material, an amorphous solid with time- and temperature-dependent properties. Using interfacial oscillatory rheology, we found that the monolayer relaxed mechanical stresses in seconds and melted at a temperature very close to the melting transition temperature of the vesicle bilayers. These results have potential application in the design of smart foams that have temperature-tunable stability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Catanionic mixtures made with two oppositely charged surfactants have attracted much attention because of their promising bulk and interfacial properties.¹⁻³ The structure of catanionic surfactants resembles that of zwitterionic amphiphiles, such as phospholipids; however, their polar headgroup is composed of two oppositely charged groups that are not covalently bonded. Despite this structural difference, the aggregates they form in the bulk exhibit the same rich diversity of morphologies that are also observed in phospholipids; these range from stable vesicles to liquid crystals, depending on the composition, temperature, and ionic strength of the medium.^{4,5} Moreover, the decrease in surface tension caused by catanionic mixtures is greater than that caused by the ionic surfactants separately; this is primarily due to the enhanced surface coverage achieved with the mixture through the strong attractive, electrostatic interaction established between the two oppositely charged surfactants.⁶ These properties are of great relevance for potential applications of catanionic mixtures as substitutes for phospholipids in materials science⁷ and as emulsion stabilizers.⁸ Furthermore, catanionic mixtures have recently been used to make foams with outstanding stability.⁹ Therefore, in this article, we focus on the adsorption, organization, and rheology of catanionic mixtures at the air/ water interface to elucidate the mechanisms underlying these foaming properties.

The catanionic mixture of myristic acid ($C_{13}COOH$) and cetyl trimethylammonium chloride (CTACl) at the particular ratio of 2 : 1 in aqueous medium forms a dispersion of stable, positively charged catanionic vesicles with diameters ranging from 2 to $5\mu m$.^{7,10,11} This dispersion also contains $10^{-4}M$ "free" CTA⁺ surfactant molecules as determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy, in the form of either monomers or small CTA⁺-rich catanionic micelles that are not eliminated by dialysis.¹⁰ By contrast, the concentration of free fatty acid (in the form of either $C_{13}COOH$ or $C_{13}COO^-$) is negligible, below the detection threshold of NMR spectroscopy.¹⁰ This particular 2:1 ratio of surfactants in the vesicles, along with the concentration of free surfactant molecules in coexistence with these vesicles, is reached after dialysis; it is independent of the initial concentrations, indicating that the system might be in thermodynamic equilibrium.¹⁰ In addition, these catanionic vesicles resemble those prepared from saturated phospholipids, such as 1,2-dipalmitoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DPPC), whose bilayers are in the so-called gel state at room temperature. However, they exhibit unusually large compression (E) and bending (κ) moduli, with typical values around 600mN/m and $2000k_B T$, respectively as measured by atomic force microscopy,¹¹ and unusually high melting temperatures, $T_m = 57^\circ C$.¹²

As previously reported, the dynamic tension of the air/water interface of this dispersion exhibits two decays.^{9,13} After the faster decay, the interfacial tension is approximately 60mN/m, because of the adsorption of the free CTA⁺ surfactant molecules present in the dispersion. However, the slight decrease in interfacial tension caused by the rapid adsorption of the free CTA⁺ molecules does not lead to the surface coverage needed for foam generation.^{9,13} It is only after the second decay, to a value of approximately 28mN/m, that the air/water interface

is sufficiently covered. The time scale of this second decay is much longer than typical foaming times. Therefore, the presence of catanionic vesicles is critical for foam generation;⁹ they provide enhanced bulk viscoelastic properties to the aqueous medium,¹⁴ which significantly retard foam drainage,¹⁵ thus providing time for the bubble surfaces to be covered. However, the underlying physical mechanism responsible for the very slow but dramatic second decay in interfacial tension has not been fully clarified. Two plausible scenarios have been proposed: the presence of an electrostatic adsorption barrier caused by the rapid adsorption of the cationic CTA⁺ surfactant molecules or the slow release of catanionic surfactants from the vesicles.^{9,13} We shall show here that the second decay is likely to be due to the latter mechanism. In addition, the outstanding stability of these foams has been attributed to the marked viscoelastic properties of the aqueous medium and the observed jamming of the vesicles confined in the liquid films and plateau borders between bubbles.⁹ Tightly packed vesicles minimize drainage and strongly reduce bubble coalescence. It has been suggested that the solid-like character of the vesicles could play a key role in foam stability.⁹ To clarify this issue, we present further investigations into the shear mechanical properties of the layers adsorbed at the air/water interface of the dispersion.

To easily visualize the air/water interface and to access the interfacial shear rheological properties, we conducted experiments using planar air/water interfaces as models for bubble surfaces. We used Brewster angle and confocal microscopy to observe the formation of the interfacial layers and their time evolution (section 3). We observed phase-coexistence domains at the air/water interface of the dispersion; this provides direct evidence of catanionic surfactant release from vesicles, which is the mechanism responsible for the good surface coverage of the bubbles. After monolayer formation, successive vesicle layers pack below this surface monolayer, hindering surfactant desorption. We measured the interfacial shear properties of the air/water interface as detailed in section 4. The response of the air/water interface to shear was found to resemble that of soft glassy materials,¹⁶ in other words, that of amorphous soft solids with a characteristic structural relaxation. The temperature dependence of the mechanical properties of this interfacial layer is similar to that of the constituent vesicles, as shown in section 5, which confirms that the solid-like character of the vesicle bilayers plays a key role.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Preparation of Vesicular Catanionic Dispersions. Robust catanionic vesicles in the gel state were prepared from mixtures of myristic acid (C₁₃COOH, Fluka; $M_w = 228$ g/mol, $T_m = 54.4^\circ\text{C}$, recrystallized twice from hot acetonitrile) and cetyl trimethylammonium chloride (CTACl, Sigma; $M_w = 320$ g/mol, $T_m = 232 - 237^\circ\text{C}$, cmc = 0.36 g/L) in a 2:1 proportion in Milli-Q water at 1wt%. The mixture was homogenized by being stirred for 3 days at 50°C. Note that the homogenization step was performed at a temperature lower than the melting temperatures of both surfactants, but high enough to allow the dis-

solution of $C_{13}COOH$ crystals by CTACl. This yielded a white homogeneous dispersion, which was dialyzed against a 100-fold volume of water (SpectraPor regenerated cellulose bilayers, 10 kDa cutoff), with the bath changed after 1, 4, 24, 48, and 120 h. This dialysis eliminated the inorganic ions (HCl) released through the formation of the mixed surfactant bilayers and allowed the stabilization of the catanionic vesicles, which otherwise tend to aggregate as a result of the screening of electrostatic interactions.¹⁰ This preparation procedure yields dispersions of positively charged vesicles with nearly spherical shapes, sizes in the range of $2 - 5\mu\text{m}$ in diameter, and high rigidity that remain stable for years. The vesicles coexist with small concentrations of free CTA⁺ ($\sim 10^{-4}\text{M}$), in the form of either free molecules or catanionic micelles, that are not eliminated by dialysis at this particular composition, as measured previously by ¹H NMR spectroscopy; by contrast, the concentration of free myristate molecules ($C_{13}COOH$ and $C_{13}COO^-$) is negligible ($< 10^{-5}\text{M}$)^{7,13} The initial dispersion (1wt%) was diluted to the desired concentrations for the experiments.

2.2. Brewster Angle Microscopy (BAM). The textures of the catanionic layers adsorbed at the air/water interface were visualized by Brewster angle microscopy (BAM). We used a MiniBAM apparatus (Nanofilm Technologie GmbH, Göttingen, Germany). The setup consisted of a laser diode (30 mW and 660 nm) that produced a nearly linear polarized beam (p/s = 100/1), sent onto the aqueous phase at an angle of $52 - 54^\circ$, ensuring Brewster's condition, that is, no reflection for an ideally sharp interface. The presence of an interfacial layer resulted in a small reflected intensity (typically, 10^{-6} times the incident beam intensity), but sufficient to detect the eventual presence of domains in the layer, because of their different refractive indices. The images were recorded using a charge-coupled-device (CCD) camera (60 Hz). To filter the residual s-component background, a positioned analyzer was placed just before the CCD camera. The resolution of this imaging system was below $20\mu\text{m}$, and the field of view, which exhibited very low geometrical distortion, was $4.8 \times 6.4\text{mm}^2$.

2.3. Confocal Microscopy. Confocal microscopy observations were performed with an Olympus BX-UCB microscope equipped with a Fluoview FV1000 confocal head. The samples were labeled with Oregon green 488 isothiocyanate (Invitrogen) excited at 488 nm, and the emitted fluorescence was collected through a 505 – 526 nm filter. We estimated the thickness of the vesicle layers present at the air/ water interface by moving the microscope objective in the z direction with a resolution of $1\mu\text{m}$. We verified that the diameter of the vesicles equaled their apparent height to ensure that the movement of the objective in the z direction equivalently moved the z focal plane, within the considered experimental error.

2.4. Interfacial Shear Oscillatory Rheology. The interfacial shear properties of the catanionic dispersions were studied using a standard rotational rheometer (Anton Paar Physica MCR 301) with an embedded interfacial rheology system

(IRS).¹⁷ The IRS consisted of a biconical disk (disk radius $R_2 = 34.14$ mm, cone angle $\alpha = 5^\circ$, and cone penetration depth $h_2 = 2.205$ mm) coupled to a top-driven motor and a torque and normal force transducer unit. The measuring cell consisted of a cup made of glass (cup inner radius $R_1 = 40.00$ mm and cup height $h_1 = 45.00$ mm), covered by an insulating jacket and fixed to the bottom part of the rheometer with a flange. The whole device was mounted on an antivibration table (Technical Manufacturing Corp., Peabody, MA). Once the solution had been poured into the cup, the disk was positioned at the interface using the normal force transducer. Thus, the solution level H_1 was determined by slowly approaching the disk while measuring the normal force ($H_1 = H_0 + h_2$, where H_0 is the gap value for which the normal force changes the most). We performed strain-controlled experiments of the adsorbed catanionic layers using oscillation mode, in which the disk oscillates at a controlled angular frequency, ω , with an amplitude of $\gamma_0[\gamma(t) = \gamma_0 e^{i\omega t}]$ while the cup remains stationary. In the small strain limit (i.e., in the linear regime), the stress response of the surface layer is given by $s(t) = G^*(\omega)\gamma(t)$, where $G^*(\omega) = G'(\omega) + iG''(\omega)$ is the complex shear modulus and G' and G'' are the storage and loss moduli, respectively. Viscoelastic systems generally behave as elastic solids at small strains but flow at larger strains. When there is only one relaxation time, G' and G'' usually follow the Maxwell model

$$G'(\omega) \propto \frac{(\omega\tau_0)^2}{1 + (\omega\tau_0)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad G''(\omega) \propto \frac{\omega\tau_0}{1 + (\omega\tau_0)^2} \quad (1)$$

with τ_0 being the characteristic relaxation time. In the nonlinear region, for soft solids, the relaxation time usually decreases when the shear rate increases as

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \frac{1}{\tau_0} + K\dot{\gamma}_0^\nu \quad (2)$$

where $\dot{\gamma}_0 = \gamma_0\omega$ is the strain-rate amplitude, K is a phenomenological constant, and ν a phenomenological positive exponent. The proposed scaling behavior (eq 2), namely, strain-rate frequency superposition (SRFS), was investigated in this study.¹⁸

Because the interfacial stresses exerted by the catanionic layers are dissipated into the bulk phase, surface and bulk flows are coupled; thus, the experimentally measured torque exerted on the disk is due not only to the interface but also to the bulk phase. Therefore, after data acquisition, we performed numerical evaluation of the interfacial rheological parameters using the commercial software developed by Anton Paar on the basis of the interfacial and bulk velocity distributions obtained by Oh and Slattery.¹⁹ The surface analysis requires knowledge of the solution bulk viscoelasticity, which we measured previously using a double Couette geometry.⁹

3. ADSORPTION OF THE CATIONIC LAYERS AT THE AIR/WATER INTERFACE OF THE DISPERSIONS

The equilibrium surface tension, σ_0 , of cationic dispersions is typically lower than those of the solutions of each ionic surfactant separately.⁶ We recently reported a nearly concentration-independent σ_0 value of 28mN/m for cationic mixtures in the concentration range between 0.001 and 0.1 wt %. This is much lower than that of the CTA⁺ surfactant alone, even at concentrations, c , higher than its critical micelle concentration, cmc [$\sigma_0^{\text{CTA}^+}(c \geq \text{cmc}) \approx 34\text{mN/m}$]. This demonstrates the strong synergism exhibited by the mixture.⁹

The dynamic surface tension, $\sigma(t)$, of the dispersions presents two decays, as shown in Figure 1.^{9,13} After a rapid decay, σ reaches a value of 60mN/m, which is attributed to the adsorption of the small amount of free CTA⁺ surfactant present in the aqueous dispersion of vesicles. After a second and much slower decay, σ reaches its final equilibrium value of $\sigma_0 \approx 28$ mN/m. Note that the surface tension measurements were made with the rising bubble method, and that one could possibly wonder if the fact that the monolayer is solid-like could affect the bubble shape. We will see later that the relaxation times are slow, on the order of seconds. We checked that oscillatory compressions of the bubble at low frequencies did not change the value of the equilibrium surface tension, demonstrating that the solid character of the monolayer did not perturb the measurement.

Two plausible scenarios were proposed previously for the slow decay: the presence of an electrostatic adsorption barrier or the slow release of surfactants from vesicles.^{9,13} To distinguish between these two scenarios, we visualized the air/water interface using Brewster angle microscopy (BAM). We used a highly dilute cationic dispersion, $c = 0.001\text{wt}\%$, to observe all of the steps of the adsorption process. The air/water interface remained homogeneous during the first decay in surface tension. This is consistent with the adsorption of CTA⁺ surfactant molecules, which form homogeneous, dilute monolayers that do not measurably modify the reflective properties of the surface, as shown in the BAM images in Figure 1a-c. At longer times, we observed the formation of dense (bright) domains in coexistence with the dilute continuous phase as shown in Figure 1d,e. The surface monolayer was highly inhomogeneous, and the domains were not equally distributed over the entire continuous phase. The domains are still observed after the second decay in surface tension. At longer times, a homogeneous dense monolayer formed, as shown in Figure 1f. Although this monolayer appeared as a homogeneous film by BAM, we cannot exclude the presence of domains with sizes smaller than the resolution limit of BAM. However, this scenario is unlikely because previous neutron scattering experiments performed on lamellar stacks demonstrated a two-dimensional liquid-like local order for the alternate distribution of cationic and anionic headgroups²⁰ and thus the absence of any lateral phase segregation.¹² The rigidity of this layer is remarkable: its compression elastic modulus E was larger than 800mN/m (as

shown at the top of Figure 1).⁹ This strong increase of the elasticity coincided with the surface tension reaching a stationary value of σ_0 , as shown in Figure 1.

Monolayers of the cationic surfactant CTA⁺ alone are homogeneous at all concentrations. Therefore, the catanionic surfactant C₁₃COO⁻/CTA⁺ must be responsible for the observed coexistence of phases. Similar phase coexistence textures at the air/water interface were previously reported for spread monolayers of catanionic mixtures^{21,22} or phospholipids.^{23,24} Phospholipid monolayers are usually spread at the water surface using a volatile organic solvent that later evaporates. However, they can also be prepared by the adsorption of vesicles.²⁵ Schindler²⁵ showed the spontaneous formation of a monolayer at the air/water interface of a fresh vesicle dispersion. The vesicles, because of the initial absence of a monolayer, directly contacted the water surface and disintegrated into surface lipids, significantly decreasing the interfacial tension. In our experiments, the high surface tension of the initially bare air/water interface decreased slightly upon the adsorption of the free CTA⁺ surfactant molecules present in the dispersion, but the interfacial tension achieved, still being high, drove the spontaneous formation at the air/water interface of a catanionic monolayer from the vesicles. The spontaneous formation of lipid interfacial monolayers from vesicles was further demonstrated by Nag et al.²⁶ They measured the change in surface tension caused by the adsorption of DPPC vesicles using a Wilhelmy plate and fluorescence microscopy to relate the increase in the packing density of the surface lipid monolayer with time to the appearance of liquid-condensed (LC) domains in an initially liquid-expanded (LE) monolayer.²⁶ It is therefore likely that the same mechanism drives the formation of LC domains (the dense phase) in an LE phase (the dilute phase) at the air/water interface in the case of the catanionic mixture under study in this work.

To further confirm this interpretation, we studied more concentrated aqueous dispersions of catanionic vesicles using confocal microscopy and concentrations ranging from 0.01 to 0.1 wt %. As shown in Figure 2, confocal micrographs taken with the focal plane located 1 – 2 μ m below the air/water interface of the dispersion revealed the presence of intact catanionic vesicles underneath the dense interfacial catanionic monolayer. For $c = 0.01\text{wt}\%$, no significant creaming of vesicles at the air/water interface was observed after 10 min, in good agreement with dynamic interfacial tension measurements, because the second decay for this concentration occurred after $\tau_2 \approx 20$ min.⁹ After that time, the presence of vesicles close to the air/water interface was significant, as shown in the confocal microscope image taken after 120 min. For $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$, the reported time for the second decay in the interfacial tension measurements was shorter ($\tau_2 \approx 8$ min),⁹ in good agreement with our observation of vesicles very close to the air/water interface at that time. Our results indicate that, at first, vesicles desintegrate (see BAM images in Figure 1c-f), but after a certain time, further desintegration is prevented by the spontaneous formation of the catanionic surface monolayer, which avoids the direct contact of the vesicles with air (see confocal microscope images in Figure 2). Therefore, we can conclude that it is the release of catanionic surfactant molecules from the vesicles at

the air/water interface that causes the dramatic second decrease in the surface tension in these dispersions.

Despite the second decay occurring at quite long times, ranging from approximately 30 min for $c = 0.001\text{wt}\%$ to approximately 8 min for $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$,⁹ its abrupt nature indicates that vesicle disintegration at the air/water interface is a very fast process. After the dense surface catanionic monolayer had been built and the surface tension had equilibrated, we still observed a layer of intact vesicles very close to the water surface (see confocal microscope images in the leftmost panel of Figure 2). In similar experiments, Schindler demonstrated that vesicles are equilibrated with the interfacial monolayer because the vesicles that have released molecules toward the interface are replaced by diffusion with new vesicles in the dispersion;²⁵ once the surface tension reaches an equilibrium value, the incoming vesicles remain intact. However, whether the composition of the surfactant film is identical to that of the vesicle bilayers after equilibration remains to be elucidated.

The volume fraction of vesicles interacting with the catanionic monolayer was found to significantly exceed that in the vesicle dispersion when equilibrium was established (i.e., $\sigma_0 = 28\text{mN/m}$). Furthermore, we observed that vesicles continued to cream toward the air/water interface at longer times, yielding a thick interfacial layer. This creaming process was mainly driven by buoyancy forces, as further discussed next. After the formation of the condensed monolayer through the release of catanionic surfactant molecules from vesicles, we measured the thickness h of the dense creamed layer of vesicles as a function of time by confocal microscopy. For this purpose, we performed an analysis of the intensity profile over a z stack. Two major changes in intensity were measured: The first one, corresponding to the dispersion surface, was always clearly visualized. However, the second one, which corresponds to the bottom of the creamed vesicle layer was more difficult to establish. This was the main source of error in our experimental determination of the vesicle layer thickness. We found that the film thickness first increased almost linearly with time as shown in Figure 3. From the slope, we obtained a creaming rate, $u \approx \Delta h/\Delta t$, of $3.0 \pm 0.5\mu\text{ m/min}$ for $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$. The thickness value measured after 80 h deviated from the linear tendency, suggesting that there was a limiting thickness value.

When a catanionic mixture at $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$ was centrifuged at 5500 rpm for 4 h, the bulk dispersion phase separated, and the vesicles were collected in the upper phase, which points out the role played by gravitational forces in the creaming process. However, the creaming rate that we measured was significantly lower than the settling velocity of an isolated vesicle in the absence of the others, U_0 , calculated solely from the competition between the gravitational force (buoyancy) and the viscous resistance (drag), which opposes the creaming because of the friction with the liquid (Stoke's law): $U_0 = \sqrt{2/9 (\Delta\rho R^2 g/\mu)}$, where g is the constant of gravitational acceleration, R is the radius of the vesicle, $\Delta\rho$ is the mass density difference between the vesicles and the dispersion medium, and μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid ($\mu = 0.01\text{ g cm}^{-1}\text{ s}^{-1}$ for water at 20°C). The number of catanionic molecules N forming the vesicle membrane can be approximated as $N \approx 2(4\pi R^2)/a_0$,²⁷ where R is the

vesicle radius and a_0 is the average optimal packing area of the cationic head-group per surfactant chain. For typical values of $R \approx 2\mu\text{ m}$ and $a_0 \approx 20\text{ \AA}^2$,²⁰ we estimate $N \approx 5 \times 10^8$. This yields a mass density difference between the vesicles and the dispersion medium of approximately 0.035 kg/m^3 and, thus, $U_0 \approx 17.8\mu\text{ m/min}$, which is 6 times larger than that experimentally measured value. This is likely due to the presence of hydrodynamic interactions in the dispersion, which increases the viscous drag due to crowding and deformation of the vesicles and thus decreases the creaming rate. This is formally expressed as $u = K(\phi)U_0$, where $K(\phi)$ is a function that depends on the vesicle volume fraction, ϕ , and accounts for those hydrodynamic interactions.²⁸ For $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$, we estimate $\phi \approx 0.16$ and thus $K(\phi) \approx 0.4$, which yields $u \approx 7\mu\text{ m/min}$, close to the experimental value. Because the vesicles under study were deformable and charged, use of the hard-sphere model is an oversimplification; however, it was still able to account for the trend observed.

Additionally, we observed a limit value for the final thickness of the creamed layers of vesicles underneath the air/water interface. This corresponds to the situation in which the volume fraction of vesicles in the bulk is negligible. Simple geometrical considerations support this hypothesis. We used a circular trough with a typical radius of 1 cm and a typical height of 1 cm to perform the confocal observations; thus, the surface area in the trough available for the adsorption of cationic vesicles was $A_T \approx 3\text{ cm}^2$, and the available sample volume was $V_T \approx 3\text{ cm}^3$. For $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$, the number of vesicles present in the trough was $N_V \approx 1.3 \times 10^{10}$, which yields a limiting film thickness of $2000\mu\text{ m}$, close to that observed. For $c = 0.01\text{wt}\%$, this limiting thickness should be reduced by an order of magnitude, consistent with the data shown in Figure 3.

Even though no significant change was observed in the packing of the first layer of vesicles with time, we observed slow (on the order of hours to days) rearrangements of vesicles in the successive layers. These rearrangements yielded lamellar phases, as shown in Figure 4. The rearrangements started after 2 h in the more concentrated sample but at a longer time in the dilute case. Such rearrangement is a very slow process that can take several weeks or even months to be completed.

All of these observations are in good agreement with the scenario depicted in Figure 5. At short times, the free cationic CTA⁺ surfactant adsorbs at the air/water interface, yielding a liquid-expanded monolayer, as illustrated schematically in panel 2 of Figure 5 and supported by BAM images in Figure 1a-c. Later, some of the vesicles in the aqueous dispersion reach the air/water interface, where a sudden release of cationic surfactant molecules from the vesicle bilayer occurs, favored by the energy gained by decreasing the surface tension. The released cationic molecules efficiently cover the air/water interface, yielding a more compact monolayer with the appearance of LC domains floating within the LE matrix, as illustrated schematically in panel 3 of Figure 5 and supported by the BAM images in Figure 1d,e. At the end of the release process, a homogeneous liquid-condensed monolayer is obtained (BAM image in Figure 1f). At longer times, no significant changes are observed in the upper surface monolayer (confocal images in the rightmost panels of Figure 2).

However, driven by buoyancy forces and hydrodynamic interactions between vesicles, vesicles cream up, yielding a very thick vesicle layer underneath the surface monolayer, as illustrated schematically in panels 4 and 5 of Figure 5 and supported by the experimental data shown in Figure 3. This thick layer of vesicles rearranges at long times, and lamellar phases are observed under the interfacial catanionic monolayer at quite long times, as illustrated schematically in panel 6 of Figure 5 and supported by the confocal images shown in Figure 4. These phases were never observed to fully cover the surface.

4. INTERFACIAL SHEAR PROPERTIES OF CATANIONIC LAYERS

In our previous work, we investigated the bulk and interfacial shear rheological properties of these catanionic dispersions.⁹ The bulk viscosity was found to be strongly concentration-dependent. The solutions become non-Newtonian at high enough concentrations ($c = 0.5\text{wt}\%$). Thus, we limited the interfacial measurements to dilute samples in which the shear response of the bulk phase is Newtonian. For $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$, we measured a frequency-independent bulk viscosity value of $\eta = 0.007\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$.⁹ The interfacial measurements were performed at least 15 min after the catanionic dispersion was poured into the interfacial rheology cell, ensuring that the monolayer adsorbed at the air/water interface was fully homogeneous. To isolate the interfacial response from the response of the bulk, we solved the Stokes equations at low Reynolds number as detailed in section 2.^{17,19}

We found that the interfacial shear response of the catanionic layers resembles that of bulk soft glassy materials, such as concentrated dispersions, emulsions, foams, or polymers.¹⁸ The linear viscoelastic behavior of the mixture is characterized by a crossover from a liquid-like to a solid-like behavior at low frequencies, as shown in Figure 6 for the catanionic mixture at $c = 0.01\text{wt}\%$, with a crossover frequency of $f_c = 0.13\text{ s}^{-1}$. This crossover frequency reflects the time scale of the structural relaxation in the catanionic layer, in analogy with the picture of a supercooled fluid.²⁹ The relaxation time is $\tau_0 = 7.7\text{ s}$. A Maxwell model does not account for the experimental trend, overestimating the values of G' and G'' around the crossover frequency as shown in Figure 6.

Typically, if one wants to discern the effects of the strain rate on the time scale of a structural relaxation process, shear rheology measurements must be performed at constant strainrate amplitude. The measurements shown in Figure 6, however, were performed with varying strain-rate amplitude, which made it difficult to discern the effects of strain rate on the relaxation process. To circumvent this problem, we improved the characterization of the surface layers by applying strain-rate frequency superposition (SRFS) to the catanionic layers (see section 2.4 for details):¹⁸ The strain rate was maintained constant at values ranging from 0.01 to 2.0 s^{-1} by simultaneously varying the strain amplitude and the frequency, as shown in Figure 7a. The dependence of G' and G'' on

frequency for the different strain rates measured is shown in Figure 7b. All of these measurements showed a crossover from fluid-like to solid-like behavior, with the crossover frequency shifting toward larger values at increasing strain rate. This means that the characteristic time scale of the structural relaxation process is driven by the applied strain-rate amplitude and forces it to a higher frequency with increasing shear rate, as shown in Figure 7c.¹⁸

We found $\tau_0 = (6.2 \pm 1.3)\text{s}$, in good agreement with the value obtained in the linear response regime (Figure 6) by fitting the experimental data in Figure 7 c to eq 2. The reproducibility of the measurements was very good, even though the thickness of the catanionic layers continued to increase during these measurements, as shown in Figure 3. This suggests that the interaction between the vesicles and the catanionic monolayer was weak enough to avoid interference during the surface rheology measurements. To further confirm this hypothesis, we studied the aging of the interfacial catanionic layer as shown in Figure 7d. We used a more concentrated aqueous dispersion of catanionic vesicles ($c = 0.1$ wt %) in this experiment because, for higher dispersion concentrations, creaming occurs more rapidly, as previously demonstrated by the experimental data summarized in Figure 3. This allows one to monitor the evolution of G' and G'' with time due to vesicle creaming without the risk of significant evaporation that would cause an inaccurate positioning of the bicone at the water surface. After 4 h, the layer of vesicles adsorbed underneath the catanionic layer, which was likely on the order of 1 mm in thickness (Figure 3), caused a very small increase in the storage modulus ($\Delta G'/G'_{4\text{ h}} \approx 10\%$), as shown in Figure 7d. Note that the viscosity of the creamed vesicle layer was certainly higher than that of the initial solution. Assuming that creaming stopped when the storage modulus of the vesicle layer became nonzero, the local viscosity in the creamed layer is expected to be less than $0.1 \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$ ⁹, that is, only at most 10 times larger than the initial dispersion viscosity. Moreover, the thickness of this layer was small compared to that of the thickness of the water layer moving along with the sheared surface (typically on the order of the distance between the bicone tip and the container, i.e., about 6 mm). The overall additional correction to the dispersion viscosity should therefore be small.

The experimental value of the characteristic structural relaxation time of the catanionic layers ($\tau_0 = 6.2 \text{ s}$) is significantly lower than the structural relaxation time of bulk suspensions, emulsions, or associative polymer systems for which the crossover frequency is inaccessible in the linear regime ($f_c < 0.016 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and thus $\tau_0 > 60 \text{ s}$).¹⁸ Unlike three-dimensional glasses composed of microparticles, micrometersized droplets, or macromolecules, the quasi-two-dimensional catanionic layer adsorbed at the air/water interface of these dispersions is made of small molecules, thus exhibiting a faster dynamics, because the interaction of this first monolayer with the layer of micrometer-sized vesicles underneath has been shown to be weak (Figure 7d).

Even though we have shown that the main contribution of the shear response comes from the catanionic monolayer adsorbed at the air/water interface of the dispersion, which is almost decoupled from the layers made of stable vesicles underneath, it is adequate to treat the system as a whole, because it is the

complete system, the entire catanionic thick layer, that likely causes foam superstability. Even though our air/water surfaces were planar and horizontal, one can imagine that similar driving and compaction mechanisms take place in a foam because of the presence of drainage. The gravity-driven flow of the dispersion between bubbles brings vesicles to the surface and also increases the local concentration of vesicles by trapping and compacting them in the liquid films separating the bubbles and in the Plateau borders.² Both coalescence and coarsening should be significantly slowed in the system as a result of the high compression and shear moduli of the catanionic monolayer. Thick layers are also known to slow Ostwald ripening,³⁰ and they should efficiently prevent coalescence as well. These properties enable foam stability for several weeks or months.⁹

5. TEMPERATURE-DRIVEN MELTING OF THE CATANIONIC MONOLAYER

Because of the saturated character of the aliphatic chains of the surfactants used, the catanionic vesicle bilayers were in the gel state and were thus extremely rigid; they had typical compression and bending moduli of approximately 600mN/m and $2000k_B T$, respectively.¹¹ The melting temperature of the catanionic surfactants forming the vesicle bilayer was 57°C. Above this temperature, the vesicle bilayers became fluid.

We found that the mechanical properties of dense catanionic monolayers at the air/water interface bear some resemblance to those of catanionic vesicle bilayers. We measured G' and G'' as functions of temperature, heating the catanionic sample at a constant rate of $Q = 0.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. These oscillatory measurements were performed at constant strain amplitude ($\gamma_0 = 0.01\%$) and frequency ($f = 1 \text{ s}^{-1}$), in the linear regime ($\dot{\gamma} = 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$), for a catanionic mixture at $c = 0.01\text{wt}\%$ after 30 min of adsorption. A dramatic decrease in both shear moduli was observed with increasing temperature, as shown in Figure 8a. Furthermore, the initially solid-like catanionic layer became liquid-like at $T_m \approx 53^\circ\text{C}$. Hence, we suggest that the gel-tofluid transition in the vesicle bilayers also occurs in the surface monolayers at increasing temperature, that is, melting of the saturated hydrocarbon chains of the surfactants. However, the decrease in G' started almost 10°C below T_m ; therefore, we cannot discard the possible link of this peculiar mechanical softening to a change in the ionization state of the fatty acid molecules upon heating. In addition, Figure 8a shows a significant increase in G'' before T_m , which might be due to an improper accounting for the bulk viscosity close to the surface, which might still be larger than the average viscosity of the dispersion.

The crossover frequency, which reflects the structural relaxation of the catanionic layer shifted to higher frequency above the transition temperature ($T_m \approx 53^\circ\text{C}$), as shown in Figure 8b. This indicates that the catanionic monolayer relaxed more rapidly at higher temperatures.

To further confirm that it is the melting of the catanionic surfactant molecules that causes the melting of the adsorbed catanionic monolayer, we studied the reversibility of the observed transition. Figure 9 shows that the solid properties of the catanionic monolayer adsorbed at the water surface were recovered when the sample was cooled after heating. However, the possibility of a change in the ionization state of the fatty acid molecules adsorbed at the air/water interface upon heating still cannot be discarded.

Recently, the adsorption at the air/water interface of multilamellar tubes from a dispersion was demonstrated.³¹ The behavior of that system bears some resemblance to that of the catanionic vesicle dispersion described in this article. The tubes were shown to have a temperature-tunable diameter at the interface, similar to their behavior in bulk, and to experience a strong mechanical softening with increasing tube diameter. Furthermore, those structural changes were reversible upon an increase or decrease in temperature. This allowed the use of that system to fabricate smart foams, with tunable stability, depending on temperature.³² Foams prepared by catanionic dispersions could have this same potential.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have provided direct evidence of catanionic monolayer formation from catanionic vesicular dispersions. The mechanical behavior of these layers resembles that of soft glassy materials. Their temperature behavior is similar to that of the vesicle bilayers, both melting at temperatures of around 55°C. When the dispersion surface is well-covered, successive layers of vesicles are jammed underneath, yielding a very thick surface layer. The foams made from vesicle dispersions are very stable against Ostwald ripening and coalescence. This is due to the extremely high compression rigidity of the catanionic monolayer, an action eventually reinforced later by the large thickness of the thick layers that form at long times.

Therefore, catanionic mixtures are not only promising substitutes for phospholipids in materials science but also potential candidates for the fabrication of smart foams with temperature-tunable stability.³²

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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Figure 1. Dynamic surface tension σ (black) and compression elastic modulus E (gray) for the cationic mixture at $c = 0.001\text{wt}\%$ measured using the rising bubble technique during the adsorption process; adapted from ref 9. The circles indicate the times at which the Brewster angle micrographs were recorded: (a) 480, (b) 960, (c) 1440, (d) 2400, (e) 3600, and (f) 5400 s. The scale bar is 1000 μm .

Figure 2. Dynamic interfacial tension curve for the cationic mixture at $c =$ (a) 0.01 and (b) 0.1wt%, measured using the rising bubble technique; adapted from ref 9 . The confocal microscope images were recorded at 600,7200 , and 180000 s . For the dilute case, after 10 min (i.e., before the second tension decay), no significant vesicle creaming was observed close to the air/water interface. For the concentrated case, creaming of vesicles close to the air/water interface was already observed after 10 min , a time by which the second decay had started. The focal plane was located at the air/water interface of the dispersion surface for imaging with a vertical resolution of 1μ m. The scale bar is 20μ m.

Figure 3. Thickening of the surface air-water film due to the creaming of vesicles to the dispersion surface, yielding a thick layer composed by intact vesicles. The thickness was measured by confocal microscopy. The dashed lines represent the estimated limits for the film thickness. The creaming rate of the vesicles was $3.0 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{ m/min}$ for $c = 0.1\text{ wt \%}$.

Figure 4. Confocal microscope images showing the rearrangement of vesicles near the air-water interface into lamellar phases. The images were obtained after 2 h and after 2 days, respectively, for the catanionic mixture at $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$, $10\ \mu\text{m}$ below the interface.

Figure 5. Schematic illustration of the structural and dynamic properties of the surface of cationic dispersions made of solid-like cationic vesicles and a small quantity of free CTA⁺.

Figure 6. Oscillatory measurements of the surface storage modulus G' and loss modulus G'' for the cationic layer adsorbed at the air-water interface for a concentration of 0.01wt% as a function of frequency at constant strain amplitude, $\gamma_0 = 0.01\%$ (left axis) and variation of the shear rate amplitude, $\dot{\gamma}_0$, for the measurement (right axis). Adapted from ref 9. The limiting high-frequency value was $G'_{\infty} = 180 \text{ mPa/m}$. The experimental data were fitted to a Maxwell model (lines).

Figure 7. (a) Variation of the strain amplitude as a function of the frequency to maintain a constant shear-rate amplitude in each measurement. (b) Oscillatory measurements of the surface storage modulus G' (solid symbols) and loss modulus G'' (open symbols) for the catanionic layer adsorbed at the air-water interface for a concentration of 0.01wt% for increasing frequency and decreasing shear strain amplitude, thus maintaining a constant shear-rate amplitude. The measurements were performed 30 min after the catanionic dispersion had been poured into the interfacial rheology cell. (c) Dependence of the inverse of the time scale of the structural relaxation process on the applied strain-rate amplitude. The dashed line is the fitting to eq 1, which yields $\tau_0 = (6.2 \pm 1.3)\text{s}$, $K = (2.26 \pm 0.05)$, and $v = (0.80 \pm 0.02)$. (d) Time variation of the surface storage modulus G' and loss modulus G'' for the catanionic layer adsorbed at the air-water interface for $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$. The aging study was performed at constant frequency ($f = 1\text{ Hz}$) and constant strain amplitude ($\gamma_0 = 0.01\%$) in the linear regime.

Figure 8. (a) Variation of G' and G'' as functions of temperature when the catanionic layer at $c = 0.01\text{wt}\%$ was sheared at constant strain amplitude ($\gamma_0 = 0.01\%$) and frequency ($f = 1 \text{ Hz}$) and the system was heated at a constant heating rate ($Q = 0.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$). (b) Variation of G' and G'' as functions of frequency at constant strain amplitude, $\gamma_0 = 0.01\%$. The measurement at 35°C was performed 30 min after the catanionic dispersion had been poured into the interfacial rheology cell; for the second measurement, the dispersion was heated to 55°C and sheared after the temperature had equilibrated.

Figure 9. Variation of the surface storage modulus G' (solid circles) and loss modulus G'' (open circles) for the cationic layer adsorbed at the air-water interface at a concentration of 0.01wt% as functions of strain amplitude at constant frequency, $f = 1$ Hz. The measurement at 35°C was performed 30 min after the cationic dispersion had been poured into the interfacial rheology cell; for the second measurement, the dispersion was heated to 55°C and sheared as soon as the temperature had equilibrated; for the third measurement, the dispersion was cooled to the initial temperature and sheared as soon as the temperature had equilibrated.